

New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Counterproposal Star and Counteroffer Wheel By Counterargument Stable Sequence As Hyper Findings On Super Gatherings

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1 SYNOPSIS

In this scientific research, (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
& |(\sum_{V_i \in V'} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V'} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V'} F(V_i))| \\
& = \min_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i)) | \\
& \quad V_j \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'', \exists V_i \in V'' : \\
& \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) > (-/ : \text{NOT DEFINED}) \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) > (-/ : \text{NOT DEFINED}) \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) > (-/ : \text{NOT DEFINED}) \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& \quad \text{then } V_j \in V'', \text{ until } V'' = V_{NSHG}\}
\end{aligned}$$

In this scientific research, new configurations are introduced for the new SuperHyperNotions, namely a Strongly Stable Sequence and a Neutrosophic Strongly Stable Sequence. Two different SuperHyperDefinitions were started for them, but research has progressed and SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperUniform, and SuperHyperClass are well-defined and well-reviewed based on them. Literature review is implemented throughout this research. To shine the light and importance of this research, a comparison between this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions and basic SuperHyperNumbers is presented. Definitions are followed by examples and examples, so clarifications are guided by various tools. Applications are designed to understand the theoretical aspect of this ongoing research. “Cancer diagnosis” are the things that are being researched to explore the challenges that make sense in ongoing research and future research. It is a special case. Cells are viewed in the intended manner. There are different types of them. Some are individual and some are well modeled by groups of cells. All these types are officially called “SuperHyperVertex”, but the relationships between them all are officially called “SuperHyperEdge”. “SuperHyperGraph” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” frameworks are selected and selected for research on “Cancer Diagnosis”. Thus, these complex and dense super-hypermodels open avenues for research on theoretical aspects and “cancer diagnosis”. Ways to pursue this scientific research have been considered. It has also

been formally collected in the form of several questions and problems. It is useful to define a “neutrosophic” version of Strongly Stable Sequence. Since there are more ways to get type results a Strongly Stable Sequence becomes more understandable. In order to master the Neutrosophic Strongly Stable Sequence, there is a need to “re-define” the concept of “Strongly Stable Sequence mastery”. SuperHyperVertices and SuperHyperEdges are assigned by alphabetical labels. In this method, the position of tags is used to assign values. Suppose a Strongly Stable Sequence. If the specified table contains “values of vertices, supervertices, edges, hyperedges, and hyperedges belonging to Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” with key points, it is redefined. ”values of vertices & number of positions in alphabet”, ”Values of SuperVertices&maximum values of its vertices”, ”values of edges&maximum values of its vertices”, ”super edge values&max values of its vertices”, “super edge values” and maximum values of its endpoints”. To get examples and structural examples, I would like to introduce the next SuperHyperClass SuperHyperGraph based on Strongly Stable Sequence. This is the original. Having the foundation of the previous definition in the SuperHyperClass type would be disciplined. If there is a need to have all Strongly Stable Sequence until Strongly Stable Sequence, then it is officially called “Strongly Stable Sequence”, but otherwise, it is not Strongly Stable Sequence. There is some explanation for the original definition titled “Strongly Stable Sequence”. These two examples are further explored and distinguished because they are characterized in the SuperHyperClass disciplinary methods based on a dominant Strongly Stable Sequence. Because of having Strongly Stable Sequence, there is a need to “re-define” the concept of “neutrosophic Strongly Stable Sequence” and “neutrosophic Strongly Stable Sequence”. SuperHyperVertices and SuperHyperEdges are assigned by alphabetical labels. In this method, the position of tags is used to assign values. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” is redefined if the desired table exists. And if the desired table exists, a Strongly Stable Sequence is redefined to a “Neutrosophic Strongly Stable Sequence”. It is useful to define a “Neutrosophic” version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there are more ways to obtain Neutrosophic type results, a SuperHyper-Neutrosophic Strongly Stable Sequence becomes more understandable. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. If the desired table exists, there are a number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. So are SuperHyperPath, SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite and SuperHyperWheel. ”Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel”. A graph is SuperHyperUniform if it is a SuperHyperGraph and the number of SuperHyperEdges elements is the same. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are a number of SuperHyperClasses as follows. It is a SuperHyperPath if there is only one SuperVertex as an intersection between two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions. If only one SuperVertex is given as an intersection between two SuperHyperEdges, it is SuperHyperCycle. It is SuperHyperStar and only one SuperVertex as intersection among all SuperHyperEdges. It is SuperHyperBipartite, and only one SuperVertex is given as the intersection between two SuperHyperEdges, and these SuperVertices, which form two distinct sets, have no SuperHyperEdge in common. This is SuperHyperMultiPartite. Only one SuperVertex is given as an intersection between two SuperHyperEdges, and these SuperVertices, which form separate multisets, have no SuperHyperEdge in common. If only one SuperHyperEdge among the given two SuperHyperEdges is a SuperHyperWheel and a SuperVertex has a SuperHyperEdge with any regular SuperVertex. SuperHyperModel suggests specific designs and specific architectures. SuperHyperModel is officially called “SuperHyperGraph” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”. In this SuperHyperModel, the “special” cells and the “special group” of cells are SuperHyperModeled as

“SuperHyperVertices” and the common and desired properties between the “special” cells and the “special group” of cells. SuperHyperModeled as “SuperHyperEdges”. Sometimes, to have a more accurate SuperHyperModel, it is useful to have some degree of determinism, uncertainty, and neutrality, in this case the SuperHyperModel is called “Neutrosophic”. In future scientific research, the foundation will be based on “diagnosis of cancer” and the results and definitions will be introduced in redeemed methods. Cancer diagnosis in long-term practice. The specific region is assigned by the model (called SuperHyperGraph) and the long cycle of movement of the cancer is determined by this scientific research. Sometimes the movement of cancer is not easy to detect, because there is certainty, uncertainty and neutrality about the movements and effects of cancer on that area. This event leads us to choose another model [which is said to be the Neutrosophic superhypergraph] in order to have a proper understanding of what happened and was done. There are some specific models, which are well known and have names, and some SuperHyperGeneral SuperHyperModels. The movements and effects of cancer in complex pathways and between complex groups of cells can be visualized with a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (-/SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The goal is to find the longest Strongly Stable Sequence or the strongest Strongly Stable Sequence in those Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels. Some general results are presented for the longest Strongly Stable Sequence called Strongly Stable Sequence and the strongest Strongly Stable Sequence called Neutrosophic Strongly Stable Sequence. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible SuperHyperPaths have only two SuperHyperEdges, but it is not enough as having at least three SuperHyperEdges is necessary to form any style of cycle. There is no form of any cycle, but literally, it is the transformation of any cycle. It literally transforms and does not form. A basic introduction to the theory of Strongly Stable Sequence Neutrosophic, SuperHyperGraphs and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs is suggested.

Keywords: Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence, Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition

AMS Subject Classification: 05C17, 05C22, 05E45

2 Applied Notions Under The Scrutiny Of The Motivation Of This Scientific Research

In this scientific research, there are ideas in the prominent frameworks of motivations. I try to bring motivations in narrative ways. Some Cells have faced attacks from the established situation with cancer attacks in this case, there is some analysis embedded in the case current situations where cells can be labeled as some groups and some groups or individuals are overlabeled, all from behaviors to overcome cancer attacks. In embedded situations, cell individuals and cell groups can be considered as “new groups”. So it encourages us to find suitable SuperHyperModels for more appropriate analysis about this dirty story. I found SuperHyperModels, officially called “SuperHyperGraphs” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. In this SuperHyperModel, cells and groups of cells are defined as “SuperHyperVertices” and relationships between individual cells and groups of cells are defined as “SuperHyperEdges”. So this is another motivation for us to do research on this SuperHyperModel based on “cancer diagnosis”. Sometimes, things get worse. The situation has passed certainty and precise style. So it is beyond them. There are three descriptions, i.e., degrees of determination, uncertainty, and neutrality, for any object based on ambiguous forms, i.e., incomplete data, imprecise data, and uncertain analysis. The second model can be considered in the previous SuperHyperModel. This is SuperHyperModel. This is SuperHyperGraph but officially

called “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Cancer is a disease, but the model is supposed to understand what happens in this phenomenon. The special case of this disease is considered and some parameters are used as consequences of the model. Cells are attacked by the disease, but the movement of cancer is in a specific area. Knowing the mind of cancer can help to find some cures for this disease. SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic Super-HyperGraph are super-hypermodels used in “cancer diagnosis” and both are the foundation of the background of this scientific research. Sometimes cancer has occurred in an area full of cells, cell groups, and embedded styles. In this section, SuperHyperModel proposes based on the links of cancer movements in the form of unity styles with the formation of design and architecture officially called “Strongly Stable Sequence”, in the themes of specialized terms and common words. Particle for direct object. Applied concepts under the investigation of the motivation of this scientific research. The “SuperHyper” prefix refers to the theme of embedded styles for background discovery for SuperHyperNotions. Cancer diagnosis in long-term practice. The specific region is assigned by the model (called SuperHyperGraph) and the long cycle of movement of the cancer is determined by this scientific research. Sometimes the movement of Cancer is not easy to identify because there is certainty, uncertainty and neutrality about the movements and effects of Cancer in that region. This event leads us to choose another model [said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph]. Easy understanding of what happened and what was done. There are some specific models that are well known and named and some general models. The movements and effects of cancer in complex pathways and between complex groups of cells can be visualized by a neutrosophic superhyperpath (-/SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The goal is to find Strongly Stable Sequence or Neutrosophic Strongly Stable Sequence for SuperHyperModels in it. Some general results are presented. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths have only two SuperHyperEdges, but it is not enough as having at least three SuperHyperEdges is necessary to form any style of cycle. There is no form of cycle, but it is literally a form of any cycle. It literally transforms and does not form.

Question 2.1. *How to define “SuperHyperNotions and to do research” to find the “Strongly Stable Sequence Rate” of any cell or groups of cells based on fixed cell or fixed group of cells broadly, “Strongly Stable Sequence Rate” based on fixed groups or fixed cells. Groups of groups of cells?*

Question 2.2. *What are the best descriptions for “diagnosing cancer” in terms of these chaotic and dense super-hypermodels in which embedded concepts are depicted?*

This motivation to find concepts to use in this dense model is called “SuperHyperGraphs”. So it motivates us to define different types of “Strongly Stable Sequence” and “neutrosophic Strongly Stable Sequence” over “superhypergraph” and “neutrosophic superhypergraph”. Then this scientific research has taken more motivations to define SuperHyperClasses and find some connections among this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions. It motivates us to obtain examples and examples to clarify the framework of this scientific research. The general results and some of the results about some of the connections are the ways that the key point of this scientific research, “diagnosis of cancer” is more understandable and clear.

The framework of this research is as follows. First, I will introduce the basic definitions to clarify the basics. In the “Introductions” subsection, basic definitions about SuperHyperGraphs and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are introduced and discussed in depth. Basic concepts are thoroughly explained and illustrated, and sometimes a literature review is used to make sense of what is to come in the coming sections. The main definitions and their explanations, along with some results on the

new concepts, Strongly Stable Sequence and Neutrosophic Strongly Stable Sequence, are specified in the sections “Strongly Stable Sequence” and “Neutrosophic Strongly Stable Sequence”. In the concept of dealing with results and in Strongly Stable Sequence to create logic about the continuation of the scientific research, the ideas of SuperHyperUniform and Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform are introduced and as their consequences, the corresponding SuperHyperClasses are specified to summarize the work done in this section, as “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”. Going back to the core concepts, clever steps towards common concepts to extend new concepts in new frameworks, SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, in “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses” sections. There is the initial scientific research on supergeneral relations and as the final and final part of the theoretical scientific research is available in the section “General results”. Some general SuperHyperRelations are fundamental and are known as fundamental SuperHyperNotions, as in “General results” were extracted and discussed. “Strongly Stable Sequence”, “Neutrosophic Strongly Stable Sequence”, “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”. There are curious questions about what has been done about SuperHyperNotions to make sense of the superiority of this scientific research and to discover the word “best” as a description and adjective of this scientific research as presented in the “Strongly Stable Sequence” section. The keyword of this scientific research was presented in the section “Applications in cancer diagnosis” with two cases and sub-sections “Case 1: Initial steps towards SuperHyperBipartite as SuperHyperModel” and “Case 2: Incremental steps towards SuperHyperMultiperdel as SuperHyper”. In the “open issues” section, there is a detailed examination and recognition of what was done in this scientific research and what happened in this scientific research in the form of “questions” and “issues” in order to understand this scientific research in an outstanding style, the advantages and limitations of this scientific research in addition to What has been done in this scientific research is stated in the “conclusion and final remarks” section.

3 Neutrosophic Preliminaries Of This Scientific Research On the Redeemed Ways

In this section, the basic material in this scientific research, is referred to [Single Valued Neutrosophic Set](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.2,p.2), [Neutrosophic Set](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.1,p.1), [Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.5,p.2), [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.7,p.3), [t-norm](**Ref. [1]**, Definition 2.7, p.3), and [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.7,p.3), [Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths] (**Ref. [1]**,Definition 5.3,p.7), and [Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)] (**Ref. [1]**,Definition 5.4,p.7). Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are addressed to **Ref. [1]**.

In this subsection, the basic material which is used in this scientific research, is presented. Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are elicited.

Definition 3.1 (Neutrosophic Set). (**Ref. [1]**,Definition 2.1,p.1).

Let X be a Eulerian-Path-Cut of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x ; then the **Neutrosophic set** A (NS A) is an object having the form

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$$

where the functions $T, I, F : X \rightarrow]-0, 1^+[$ define respectively the a

truth-membership function, an **indeterminacy-membership function**, and a **falsity-membership function** of the element $x \in X$ to the set A with the condition

$$-0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3^+.$$

The functions $T_A(x)$, $I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$ are real standard or nonstandard subsets of $] -0, 1^+ [$.

Definition 3.2 (Single Valued Neutrosophic Set). (**Ref.** [1], Definition 2.2, p.2).

Let X be a **Eulerian-Path-Cut** of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x . A **single valued Neutrosophic set** A (SVNS A) is characterized by truth-membership function $T_A(x)$, an indeterminacy-membership function $I_A(x)$, and a falsity-membership function $F_A(x)$. For each point x in X , $T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \in [0, 1]$. A SVNS A can be written as

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}.$$

Definition 3.3. The **degree of truth-membership**, **indeterminacy-membership** and **falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$T_A(X) = \min[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = \min[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$\text{and } F_A(X) = \min[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.4. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{ x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0 \}.$$

Definition 3.5 (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (**Ref.** [1], Definition 2.5, p.2).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;
- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'})) : T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);

Figure 1. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

(ix) and the following conditions hold:

$$T'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$I'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$\text{and } F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}}$$

where $i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$.

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, $I'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, and $F'_{V'}(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the ii' th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Example 3.6. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic notion, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint.
- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic notion, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a

Figure 2. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint.

- On the Figure (3), the SuperHyperNotion, namely, SuperHyperGirth, is up. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 .
- On the Figure (4), there's no empty SuperHyperEdge but E_3 are a loop SuperHyperEdge on $\{F\}$ and there are some SuperHyperEdges, namely, E_1 on $\{H, V_1, V_3\}$, alongside E_2 on $\{O, H, V_4, V_3\}$ and E_4, E_5 on $\{N, V_1, V_2, V_3, F\}$.
- On the Figure (5), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge.
- On the Figure (6), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge.
- On the Figure (7), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge.
- On the Figure (8), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge.
- On the Figure (9), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge.
- On the Figure (10), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge.
- On the Figure (11), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge.

Figure 3. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 4. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 5. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs mentioned as the SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 6. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 7. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs depicted SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 8. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with dense SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 9. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a messy SuperHyper-Modeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 10. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with highly-embedding-connected SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 11. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

- On the Figure (12), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 298
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- On the Figure (13), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 300
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- On the Figure (14), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 302
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- On the Figure (15), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 304
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- On the Figure (16), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 306
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- On the Figure (17), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 308
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- On the Figure (18), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 310
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- On the Figure (19), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 312
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- On the Figure (20), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 314
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- On the Figure (21), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 316
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- On the Figure (22), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 318
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Figure 12. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with highly-multiple-connected-style SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 13. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 14. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 15. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with Linearly-Connected SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 16. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 17. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a Linearly-over-packed SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 18. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 19. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 20. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 21. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 22. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Definition 3.7 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;
- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**;
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**;
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**;
- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**;
- (vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**.

If we choose different types of binary operations, then we could get hugely diverse types of general forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG).

Definition 3.8 (t-norm). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3).

A binary operation $\otimes : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a **t-norm** if it satisfies the following for $x, y, z, w \in [0, 1]$:

- (i) $1 \otimes x = x$;
- (ii) $x \otimes y = y \otimes x$;
- (iii) $x \otimes (y \otimes z) = (x \otimes y) \otimes z$;

(iv) If $w \leq x$ and $y \leq z$ then $w \otimes y \leq x \otimes z$.

Definition 3.9. The **degree of truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership and falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$ (with respect to t-norm T_{norm}):

$$T_A(X) = T_{norm}[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = T_{norm}[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$\text{and } F_A(X) = T_{norm}[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.10. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0\}.$$

Definition 3.11. (General Forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;
- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'})) : T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$).

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_V(E_{i'})$, $I'_V(E_{i'})$, and $F'_V(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the ii' th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Definition 3.12 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;

- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**; 375
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**; 376
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**; 377
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- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**; 379
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- (vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**. 381
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This SuperHyperModel is too messy and too dense. Thus there's a need to have some restrictions and conditions on SuperHyperGraph. The special case of this SuperHyperGraph makes the patterns and regularities. 383
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Definition 3.13. A graph is **SuperHyperUniform** if it's SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same. 386
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To get more visions on SuperHyperUniform, the some SuperHyperClasses are introduced. It makes to have SuperHyperUniform more understandable. 388
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Definition 3.14. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as follows. 390
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- (i). It's **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions; 392
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- (ii). it's **SuperHyperCycle** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges; 394
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- (iii). it's **SuperHyperStar** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges; 396
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- (iv). it's **SuperHyperBipartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; 398
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- (v). it's **SuperHyperMultiPartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multi separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; 401
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- (vi). it's **SuperHyperWheel** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex. 404
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Example 3.15. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the notion. 407
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Example 3.16. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is up. 410
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Example 3.17. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is up. 413
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Figure 23. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath Associated to the Notions in the Example (3.15)

Figure 24. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (3.16)

Figure 25. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (3.17)

Example 3.18. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is up.

Example 3.19. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is up.

Example 3.20. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is up.

Definition 3.21. Let a pair $S = (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S . Then a sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s$$

is called a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s if either of following conditions hold:

- (i) $V_i, V_{i+1} \in E_i$;

Figure 26. Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Example (3.18)

Figure 27. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions in the Example (3.19)

Figure 28. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (3.20)

- (ii) there's a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ such that $v_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 439
- (iii) there's a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ such that $V'_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 440
- (iv) there's a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 441
- (v) there's a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 442
- (vi) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 443
- (vii) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 444
- (viii) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 445
- (ix) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$. 446
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Definition 3.22. (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths). 448

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

could be characterized as follow-up items. 449

- (i) If for all $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| = 1, |E_{j'}| = 2$, then NSHP is called **path**; 450
- (ii) if for all $E_{j'}, |E_{j'}| = 2$, and there's $V_i, |V_i| \geq 1$, then NSHP is called **SuperPath**; 451
- (iii) if for all $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| = 1, |E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **HyperPath**; 452
- (iv) if there are $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| \geq 1, |E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath**. 453
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Definition 3.23 (Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths). 455
(Ref. [1], Definition 5.3, p.7). 456

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV)

Table 1. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.27)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

have

- (i) **Neutrosophic t-strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, m, n)_{i=1}^s$; 457
- (ii) **Neutrosophic i-strength** $(m, \min\{I(V_i)\}, n)_{i=1}^s$; 458
- (iii) **Neutrosophic f-strength** $(m, n, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$; 459
- (iv) **Neutrosophic strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$. 460

Definition 3.24 (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)). (Ref. [1], Definition 5.4, p.7). 461

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called 462

- (ix) **Neutrosophic t-connective** if $T(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic t-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 463
- (x) **Neutrosophic i-connective** if $I(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic i-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 464
- (xi) **Neutrosophic f-connective** if $F(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic f-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 465
- (xii) **Neutrosophic connective** if $(T(E), I(E), F(E)) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$. 466

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic notion, there's a need to “**redefine**” the notion of “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”. The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values. 467

Definition 3.25. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. It's redefined **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** if the Table (1) holds. 468

It's useful to define a “Neutrosophic” version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's more ways to get Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic more understandable. 469

Table 2. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, Mentioned in the Definition (3.26)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Table 3. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.27)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Definition 3.26. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. There are some **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses** if the Table (2) holds. Thus Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, notion, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and SuperHyperWheel, are **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar, Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite,** and **Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel** if the Table (2) holds.

It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of a Neutrosophic notion. Since there's more ways to get type-results to make a Neutrosophic notion more Neutrosophicly understandable.

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic notion, there's a need to "redefine" the Neutrosophic notion of "Neutrosophic notion". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.27. Assume a notion. It's redefined a **Neutrosophic notion** if the Table (3) holds.

Example 3.28. Referred to the Example (3.6), assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (4).

Table 4. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0, 0, 0)
V_2	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_2	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)
V_3	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
V_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)

Table 5. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0, 0, 0)
V_2	(0.03, 0.03, 0.03)	E_2	(0, 0, 0)
V_3	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
V_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)

Table 6. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0, 0, 0)
V_2	(0.11, 0.11, 0.11)	E_2	(0, 0, 0)
V_3	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
-	-	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (5). 510
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- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (6). 512
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- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (7). 514
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4 Main Resultant 516

Definition 4.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence). 517
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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence criteria holds. 519
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$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V'} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V'} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V'} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \min_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{ |(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i)) |
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 7. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0.08, 0.08, 0.08)
V_2	(0.11, 0.11, 0.11)	E_2	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)
V_3	(0.05, 0.05, 0.05)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
V_4	(0.12, 0.12, 0.12)	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)
$\{F\}$	(0.06, 0.06, 0.06)	E_5	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)
$\{H\}$	(0.08, 0.08, 0.08)	-	-
$\{N\}$	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	-	-
$\{O\}$	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)	-	-

Figure 29. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Table 8. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

$$V_j \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'', \exists V_i \in V'' :$$

$$T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) > (- / : \text{NOT DEFINED}) \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

$$I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) > (- / : \text{NOT DEFINED}) \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

$$F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) > (- / : \text{NOT DEFINED}) \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

then $V_j \in V''$, until $V'' = V_{NSHG}$

Example 4.2. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (29), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (8).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i=1,4,6}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence criteria holds.

$$|(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,4,6}\}} T(V_i),$$

Figure 30. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 31. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 32. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 33. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 34. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 35. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 36. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 37. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 38. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 39. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 40. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 41. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Table 9. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,4,6}\}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,4,6}\}} F(V_i) \\
 & = (0.78, 0.78, 0.78) = \\
 & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i) \right) \right| \\
 & \quad V_{i=1} \in V'' = \{V_{1,4,6}\}, \exists V_{j=5} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad \text{then } V_{j=5} \in V'', \text{ but } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}, \\
 & \quad V_{i=4} \in V'' = \{V_{i=1,4-6}\}, \exists V_{j=3} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad \text{then } V_{j=3} \in V'', \text{ but } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}, \\
 & \quad V_{i=4} \in V'' = \{V_{1,3-6}\}, \exists V_{j \neq 5,6} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad \text{then } V_{j \neq 5,6} \in V'', \text{ then } V'' = V_{NSHG}. \}
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (30), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (9). 531
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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i=1,4,6}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence criteria holds. 533
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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,4,6}\}} T(V_i), \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,4,6}\}} I(V_i), \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,4,6}\}} F(V_i) \right) \right|
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 10. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.19, 0.19, 0.19)	E_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

$$\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,4,6}\}} F(V_i) |$$

$$= (0.78, 0.78, 0.78) =$$

$$= \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} | \{ (\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i)) |$$

$$V_{i=1} \in V'' = \{V_{1,4,6}\}, \exists V_{j=5} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' :$$

$$T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

$$I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

$$F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

then $V_{j=5} \in V''$, but $V'' \neq V_{NSHG}$,

$$V_{i=1} \in V'' = \{V_{i=1,4-6}\}, \exists V_{j=2} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' :$$

$$T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

$$I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

$$F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

then $V_{j=2} \in V''$, but $V'' \neq V_{NSHG}$,

$$V_{i=4} \in V'' = \{V_{i=1-2,4-6}\}, \exists V_{j=3} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' :$$

$$T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

$$I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

$$F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

then $V_{j=3} \in V''$, but $V'' \neq V_{NSHG}$,

$$V_{i=4} \in V'' = \{V_{1-2,3-6}\}, \exists V_{j \neq 5,6} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' :$$

$$T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

$$I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

$$F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$$

then $V_{j \neq 5,6} \in V''$, then $V'' = V_{NSHG}$.}

- On the Figure (31), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (10). 537
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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i=1,4}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence since the following expressions, terms and 539
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statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned} & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,4}\}} T(V_i), \\ & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,4}\}} I(V_i), \\ & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,4}\}} F(V_i))| \\ & = (0.52, 0.52, 0.52) = \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i))| \\ & \quad V_{i=1} \in V'' = \{V_{i=1,4}\}, \exists V_{j=2} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\ & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.19 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\ & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.19 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\ & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.19 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\ & \quad \text{then } V_{j=2} \in V'', \text{ but } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}, \\ & \quad V_{i=1} \in V'' = \{V_{i=1-2,4}\}, \exists V_{j=6} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\ & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\ & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\ & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\ & \quad \text{then } V_{j=6} \in V'', \text{ but } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}, \\ & \quad V_{i=4} \in V'' = \{V_{i=1-2,4,6}\}, \exists V_{j=3} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\ & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\ & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\ & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\ & \quad \text{then } V_{j=3} \in V'', \text{ but } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}, \\ & \quad V_{i=3} \in V'' = \{V_{i=1-2,3-4,6}\}, \exists V_{j=5,7} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\ & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\ & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\ & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\ & \quad \text{then } V_{j=5,7} \in V'', \text{ then } V'' = V_{NSHG}. \} \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (33), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (11).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i=1,4}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned} & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,4}\}} T(V_i), \\ & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,4}\}} I(V_i), \\ & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,4}\}} F(V_i))| \end{aligned}$$

Table 11. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.19, 0.19, 0.19)	E_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_7	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)

$$\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,4}\}} F(V_i) |$$

$$= (0.52, 0.52, 0.52) =$$

$$= \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i)) |$$

$V_{i=1} \in V'' = \{V_{i=1,4}\}, \exists V_{j=2} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' :$
 $T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.19 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$
 $I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.19 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$
 $F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.19 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$
 then $V_{j=2} \in V''$, but $V'' \neq V_{NSHG}$,
 $V_{i=1} \in V'' = \{V_{i=1-2,4}\}, \exists V_{j=6,7} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' :$
 $T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$
 $I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$
 $F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$
 then $V_{j=6,7} \in V''$, but $V'' \neq V_{NSHG}$,
 $V_{i=4} \in V'' = \{V_{i=1-2,4,6,7}\}, \exists V_{j=3} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' :$
 $T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$
 $I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$
 $F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$
 then $V_{j=3} \in V''$, but $V'' \neq V_{NSHG}$,
 $V_{i=3} \in V'' = \{V_{1-2,3-4,6,7}\}, \exists V_{j=5} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' :$
 $T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$
 $I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$
 $F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},$
 then $V_{j=5} \in V''$, then $V'' = V_{NSHG}.$

- On the Figure (35), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (12). 549
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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i=1,4}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence criteria holds. 551
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$$|(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,4}\}} T(V_i),$$

Table 12. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.19, 0.19, 0.19)	E_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,4}\}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,4}\}} F(V_i) | \\
 & = (0.52, 0.52, 0.52) = \\
 & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} | \{ \sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i) \} | \\
 & \quad V_{i=1} \in V'' = \{V_{i=1,4}\}, \exists V_{j=2} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.19 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.19 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.19 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad \text{then } V_{j=2} \in V'', \text{ but } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}, \\
 & \quad V_{i=1} \in V'' = \{V_{i=1-2,4}\}, \exists V_{j=6} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad \text{then } V_{j=6} \in V'', \text{ but } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}, \\
 & \quad V_{i=1} \in V'' = \{V_{i=1-2,4,6}\}, \exists V_{j=7} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad \text{then } V_{j=7} \in V'', \text{ but } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}, \\
 & \quad V_{i=1} \in V'' = \{V_{i=1-2,4,6,7}\}, \exists V_{j=3} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad \text{then } V_{j=3} \in V'', \text{ but } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}, \\
 & \quad V_{i=3} \in V'' = \{V_{i=1-2,3-4,6,7}\}, \exists V_{j=5} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad \text{then } V_{j=5} \in V'', \text{ then } V'' = V_{NSHG}. \}
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 13. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.19, 0.19, 0.19)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)

- On the Figure (37), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (13). 555
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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i=1,4}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence criteria holds. 557
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$$\begin{aligned}
& |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,4}\}} T(V_i), \\
& \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,4}\}} I(V_i), \\
& \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,4}\}} F(V_i))| \\
& = (0.52, 0.52, 0.52) =
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i))| \\
& \quad V_{i=1} \in V'' = \{V_{i=1,4}\}, \exists V_{j=2} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
& \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.19 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.19 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.19 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& \quad \text{then } V_{j=2} \in V'', \text{ but } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}, \\
& \quad V_{i=1} \in V'' = \{V_{i=1-2,4}\}, \exists V_{j=6} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
& \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& \quad \text{then } V_{j=6} \in V'', \text{ but } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}, \\
& \quad V_{i=1} \in V'' = \{V_{i=1-2,4,6}\}, \exists V_{j=7} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
& \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& \quad \text{then } V_{j=7} \in V'', \text{ but } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}, \\
& \quad V_{i=4} \in V'' = \{V_{i=1-2,4,6,7}\}, \exists V_{j=3} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
& \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
& \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}},
\end{aligned}$$

Table 14. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &F'_V(E_{i'}) (V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.24 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 &\text{then } V_{j=3} \in V'', \text{ but } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}, \\
 &V_{i=3} \in V'' = \{V_{1-2,3-4,6,7}\}, \exists V_{j=5} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'': \\
 &T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 &I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 &F'_V(E_{i'}) (V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 &\text{then } V_{j=5} \in V'', \text{ then } V'' = V_{NSHG}. \}
 \end{aligned}$$

Example 4.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (32), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (14).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i=5}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 &|(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=5}\}} T(V_i), \\
 &\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=5}\}} I(V_i), \\
 &\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=5}\}} F(V_i))| \\
 &= (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) = \\
 &= \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i))| \\
 &V_{i=5} \in V'' = \{V_5\}, \exists V_{j \neq 5} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'': \\
 &T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 &I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 &F'_V(E_{i'}) (V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 &\text{then } V_{j \neq 5} \in V'', \text{ then } V'' = V_{NSHG}. \}
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (34), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (15).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i=2,5}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic

Table 15. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Table 16. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence criteria holds.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=2,5}\}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=2,5}\}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=2,5}\}} F(V_i))| \\
 & = (0.52, 0.52, 0.52) = \\
 & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i))| \\
 & \quad V_{i=2} \in V'' = \{V_{i=2,5}\}, \exists V_{j=1} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad \text{then } V_{j=1} \in V'', \text{ but } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}, \\
 & \quad V_{i=5} \in V'' = \{V_{1,2,5}\}, \exists V_{j \neq 1,2,5} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad \text{then } V_{j \neq 1,2,5} \in V'', \text{ then } V'' = V_{NSHG}. \}
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (36), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (16).

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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i=2,5}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence since the following expressions, terms and

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Table 17. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence criteria holds.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=2,5}\}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=2,5}\}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=2,5}\}} F(V_i))| \\
 & = (0.52, 0.52, 0.52) = \\
 & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i))| \\
 & \quad V_{i=2} \in V'' = \{V_{i=2,5}\}, \exists V_{j=1,3} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad \text{then } V_{j=1,3} \in V'', \text{ but } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}, \\
 & \quad V_{i=5} \in V'' = \{V_{1-3,5}\}, \exists V_{j \neq 1-3,5} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad \text{then } V_{j \neq 1-3,5} \in V'', \text{ then } V'' = V_{NSHG}. \}
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (38), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (17).

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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i=2,5}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence criteria holds.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=2,5}\}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=2,5}\}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=2,5}\}} F(V_i))| \\
 & = (0.52, 0.52, 0.52) =
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 18. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i) \right) \right| \\
 &V_{i=2} \in V'' = \{V_{i=2,5}\}, \exists V_{j=1,3,4} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 &T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 &I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 &F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 &\text{then } V_{j=1,3,4} \in V'', \text{ but } V'' \neq V_{NSHG}, \\
 &V_{i=5} \in V'' = \{V_{1-5}\}, \exists V_{j \neq 1-5} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 &T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 &I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 &F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) : \text{NOT DEFINED} \neq 0.26 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 &\text{then } V_{j \neq 1-5} \in V'', \text{ then } V'' = V_{NSHG}. \}
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (39), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (18). 587
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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i=2,6,7}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence criteria holds. 589
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$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=2,6,7}\}} T(V_i), \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=2,6,7}\}} I(V_i), \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=2,6,7}\}} F(V_i) \right) \left. \right| \\
 &= (0.78, 0.78, 0.78) = \\
 &= \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i) \right) \right| \\
 &V_{i=2} \in V'' = \{V_{i=2,6,7}\}, \exists V_{j \neq 2,6,7} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 &T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 &I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 &F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 &\text{then } V_{j \neq 2,6,7} \in V'', \text{ then } V'' = V_{NSHG}. \}
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (40), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (19). 593
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Table 19. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Table 20. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_7	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i=2,7}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=2,7}\}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=2,7}\}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=2,7}\}} F(V_i))| \\
 & = (0.52, 0.52, 0.52) = \\
 & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |\{(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i)) | \\
 & \quad V_{i=2} \in V'' = \{V_{i=2,7}\}, \exists V_{j \neq 2,7} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \text{then } V_{j \neq 2,7} \in V'', \text{ then } V'' = V_{NSHG}. \}
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (41), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (20).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_{i=2}\}$. Then V' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=2}\}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=2}\}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=2}\}} F(V_i))|
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=2}\}} F(V_i) | \\
 &= (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) = \\
 &= \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} | \{ (\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i)) | \\
 & \quad V_{i=2} \in V'' = \{V_{i=2}\}, \exists V_{j \neq 2} \in V_{NSHG} \setminus V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \quad F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) = 0.26 > 0.23 = \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}}, \\
 & \text{then } V_{j \neq 2} \in V'', \text{ then } V'' = V_{NSHG}. \}
 \end{aligned}$$

5 Main Result

Theorem 5.1. (Main Result and Main Theorem).

Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar has the letter z . The notion on the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar and Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel coincides.

Proof.

(i). Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & CENTER, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 & E_2, CENTER
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence. The latter is straightforward.

(ii). Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\
 & CENTER, E_2^*
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 & E_2^*, CENTER
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.2. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence set is as follows.*

$$\{CENTER\}.$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^* \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2^*, CENTER \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.3. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence number is as follows.*

0.26.

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^*$$

$$P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2^*, CENTER$$

is a longest SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.4. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence set is as follows.*

$$\{CENTER\}.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ CENTER, E_2$$

$$P : \\ E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2, CENTER$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.5. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence number is as follows.*

0.26.

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ CENTER, E_2$$

$$P : \\ E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2, CENTER$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Definition 5.6. (Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar and Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar).

- (i). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Every pair of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices has the same maximum letter, i.e., Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices mutually has the same maximum letter. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$ is called **Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar**.
- (ii). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Every pair of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices has the same maximum letter, i.e., Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices mutually has the same maximum letter. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$ is called **Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel**.

Proposition 5.7. *Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence set is as follows.*

$$\{CENTER\}.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^*$$

$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
E_2^*, CENTER
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Proposition 5.8. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence number is lower than as follows.*

0.26.

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\
CENTER, E_2^*
\end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
E_2^*, CENTER
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Proposition 5.9. *Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence set is as follows.*

$$\{CENTER\}.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ CENTER, E_2$$

$$P : \\ E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2, CENTER$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.10. *Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence number is lower than as follows.*

$$0.26.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ CENTER, E_2$$

$$P : \\ E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2, CENTER$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.11. (*Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar and Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel*).

(i). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic CENTER has the letter maximum letter. Then the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices don't have the same maximum letter, are in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence set.

(ii). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic CENTER has the letter maximum letter. Then the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices don't have the same maximum letter, are in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence set.

Proof.

(i). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ CENTER, E_2$$

$$P : \\ E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2, CENTER$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence. The latter is straightforward.

(ii). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^*$$

$$P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2^*, CENTER$$

is a longest SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence. Thus the notion of quasi isn’t up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. □

Proposition 5.12. (*Embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar and Embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar*).

- (i). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Then *CENTER* is in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence set.
- (ii). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Then *CENTER* is in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence set.

Proof.

(i). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ CENTER, E_2$$

$$P : \\ E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2, CENTER$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There’s a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence. The latter is straightforward.

(ii). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^*$$

$$P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2^*, CENTER$$

is a longest SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There’s a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv$$

$$\begin{aligned} \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence. Thus the notion of quasi isn’t up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. □

6 Neutrosophic Applications in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition

The cancer is the Neutrosophic disease but the Neutrosophic model is going to figure out what’s going on this Neutrosophic phenomenon. The special Neutrosophic case of this Neutrosophic disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The Neutrosophic recognition of the cancer could help to find some Neutrosophic treatments for this Neutrosophic disease.

In the following, some Neutrosophic steps are Neutrosophic devised on this disease.

Step 1. (Neutrosophic Definition) The Neutrosophic recognition of the cancer in the long-term Neutrosophic function.

Step 2. (Neutrosophic Issue) The specific region has been assigned by the Neutrosophic model [it’s called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] and the long Neutrosophic cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn’t be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it’s said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what’s happened and what’s done.

Step 3. (Neutrosophic Model) There are some specific Neutrosophic models, which are well-known and they’ve got the names, and some general Neutrosophic models. The moves and the Neutrosophic traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence or the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence in those Neutrosophic Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels.

7 Case 1: The Initial Neutrosophic Steps Toward Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite as Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel

Step 4. (Neutrosophic Solution) In the Neutrosophic Figure (42), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic

Figure 42. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence

Table 21. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

featured.

By using the Neutrosophic Figure (42) and the Table (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite is obtained.

The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (42), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence.

8 Case 2: The Increasing Neutrosophic Steps Toward Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite as Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel

Step 4. (Neutrosophic Solution) In the Neutrosophic Figure (43), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured.

By using the Neutrosophic Figure (43) and the Table (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite is obtained.

The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic

Figure 43. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence

Table 22. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyper-Edges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

SuperHyperModel (43), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence. 824

9 Neutrosophic Applications in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition 825

Cancer is a neutrosophic disease, but the neutrosophic model is supposed to understand what is going on in this neutrosophic phenomenon. The special case of neutrosophic disease is considered and some parameters have been used as consequences of the model. Cells are subject to attack by the disease, but the movements of the cancer in the specific area is a matter of mind. Neutrosophic diagnosis of cancer can help in finding some Neutrosophic cures for this Neutrosophic disease. 826

In the following, several Neutrosophic stages are designed for this disease. 827

Step 1. (Neutrosophic Definition) Neutrosophic diagnosis of cancer in long-term Neutrosophic performance. 828

Step 2. (Neutrosophic Issue) The specific region is assigned by the Neutrosophic model (called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph) and the long Neutrosophic cycle of movement of cancer is identified by this scientific research. Sometimes the movement of cancer is not easy to detect, because there is certainty, uncertainty and neutrality about the movements and effects of cancer on that area. This event leads us to choose another model [which is said to be the Neutrosophic superhypergraph] in order to have a proper understanding of what happened and was done. 829

Step 3. (Neutrosophic Model) There are some specific Neutrosophic models that are well known and have names and some general Neutrosophic models. Cancer neutrosophic movements and effects in complex pathways and between complex groups of cells can be visualized by a SuperHyperPath (-/SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The goal is to find dominant neutrosophic Strongly Stable Sequence models or dominant sStrongly Stable Sequence models.

10 Wondering Open Problems But As The Directions To Forming The Motivations

In what follows, some “problems” and some “questions” are proposed.

The SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence are defined on a real-world application, titled “Cancer’s Recognitions”.

Question 10.1. *Which the else SuperHyperModels could be defined based on Cancer’s recognitions?*

Question 10.2. *Are there some SuperHyperNotions related to SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence ?*

Question 10.3. *Are there some Algorithms to be defined on the SuperHyperModels to compute them?*

Question 10.4. *Which the SuperHyperNotions are related to beyond the SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence ?*

Problem 10.5. *The SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence do a SuperHyperModel for the Cancer’s recognitions and they’re based on SuperHyperStrongly Stable Sequence, are there else?*

Problem 10.6. *Which the fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are related to these SuperHyperNumbers types-results?*

Problem 10.7. *What’s the independent research based on Cancer’s recognitions concerning the multiple types of SuperHyperNotions?*

11 Conclusion and Closing Remarks

In this section, closing and concluding remarks are presented. The drawbacks of this scientific research are shown. Some advantages and disadvantages of this scientific research are highlighted.

This scientific research uses some approaches to further understand the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs. In this effort, two SuperHyperNotions are defined on the Strongly Stable Sequence. For this reason, in the second definition, the original definition of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is redefined on the position of the alphabets. Based on the new Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph definition, the new SuperHyperNotion, Neutrosophic Strongly Stable Sequence, finds a suitable background to implement some results on. Some SuperHyperClasses and some Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses are the subjects of this scientific research on modeling areas that are subject to cancer attacks in order to recognize this disease as mentioned under the title “Cancer Diagnosis”. To formalize the SuperHyperNotion, Strongly Stable Sequence, SuperHyperClasses and new SuperHyperClasses instances are introduced. Some general results are summarized in the Strongly Stable Sequence and Neutrosophic Strongly Stable Sequence sections.

Clarifications, examples, and literature reviews go all the way. In this scientific research, the literature review has met the lines containing concepts and results. SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are super-hypermodels in “cancer diagnosis” and both are the foundation of the background of this scientific research. Sometimes cancer has occurred in an area full of cells, cell groups, and embedded styles. In this section, SuperHyperModel proposes SuperHyperNotions, formally called “Strongly Stable Sequence”, based on the connections of Cancer’s movements in the longest and strongest styles with the formation of design and architecture, in terms of terms and whispering words. . The “SuperHyper” prefix refers to the topic of embedded styles to explore the background of SuperHyperNotions. In

Table 23. A look at this scientific research and beyond

Advantages	Limitations
1. Redefining the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph	1. General Results
2. Strongly Stable Sequence	
3. Neutrosophic Strongly Stable Sequence	2. Other SuperHyperNumbers
4. modeling cancer diagnoses	
5. SuperHyperClasses	3. SuperHyperFamilies

the table (23), the advantages and ways of this scientific research are specified, pointed out and expressed.

12 Background

There are some scientific researches covering the topic of this scientific research. In what follows, there are some discussion and literature reviews about them.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph As Hyper Tool On Super Toot*” in **Ref. [1]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on general forms with introducing used neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Current Trends in Mass Communication (CTMC)*” with ISO abbreviation “*Curr Trends Mass Comm*” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 32-55.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*” in **Ref. [2]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer’s Treatments. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*” with ISO abbreviation “*J Math Techniques Comput Math*” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 35-47. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*A Research on Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic Super Hypergraph by Eulerian Super Hyper Cycles and Hamiltonian Sets as Hyper Covering Versus Super separations*” in **Ref. [3]** by Henry

Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer's Recognition. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*" with ISO abbreviation "*J Math Techniques Comput Math*" in volume 2 and issue 3 with pages 136-148. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction to Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition and Beyond*" in **Ref. [4]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*" with ISO abbreviation "*J Math Techniques Comput Math*" in volume 2 and issue 6 with pages 221-307. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph by Initial Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Initial Eulogy on Super Initial EULA*" in **Ref. [5]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research*" with ISO abbreviation "*IJPAMR*" in volume 3 and issue 2 with pages 60-88 and doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.60-88. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graph by Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut on Super EULA-Path-Cut*" in **Ref. [6]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research*" with ISO abbreviation "*IJPAMR*" in volume 3 and issue 2 with pages 102-124 and doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.102-124. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "*Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes*" in **Ref. [7]** by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*" with ISO abbreviation "*J Math Techniques Comput Math*" in volume 1 and issue 3 with pages 242-263. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. The seminal

paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*neutrosophic co-degree and neutrosophic degree alongside chromatic numbers in the setting of some classes related to neutrosophic hypergraphs*” in **Ref. [8]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on general forms without using neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Journal of Current Trends in Computer Science Research (JCTCSR)*” with ISO abbreviation “*J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res*” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 16-24. The research article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background. The research article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background. In some articles are titled “*0039 — Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph*” in **Ref. [9]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*0049 — (Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs*” in **Ref. [10]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [11]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition*” in **Ref. [12]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [13]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*” in **Ref. [14]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [15]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [16]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [17]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [18]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*” in **Ref. [19]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*” in **Ref. [20]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [21]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*” in **Ref. [17]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [22]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*” in **Ref. [23]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances*” in **Ref. [24]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With*

SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer's Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses in **Ref. [25]** by Henry Garrett (2022),
"SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer's Recognitions" in **Ref. [26]** by Henry Garrett (2022),
"Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer's Treatments" in **Ref. [27]** by Henry Garrett (2022), *"SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses"* in **Ref. [28]** by Henry Garrett (2022), *"SuperHyperMatching By (R-)Definitions And Polynomials To Monitor Cancer's Recognition In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs"* in **Ref. [227]** by Henry Garrett (2023), *"The Focus on The Partitions Obtained By Parallel Moves In The Cancer's Extreme Recognition With Different Types of Extreme SuperHyperMatching Set and Polynomial on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs"* in **Ref. [228]** by Henry Garrett (2023), *"Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer's Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer's Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs"* in **Ref. [229]** by Henry Garrett (2023), *"Indeterminacy On The All Possible Connections of Cells In Front of Cancer's Attacks In The Terms of Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique on Cancer's Recognition called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs"* in **Ref. [230]** by Henry Garrett (2023), *"Perfect Directions Toward Idealism in Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition Forwarding Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs"* in **Ref. [233]** by Henry Garrett (2023), *"Demonstrating Complete Connections in Every Embedded Regions and Sub-Regions in the Terms of Cancer's Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClique"* in **Ref. [234]** by Henry Garrett (2023), *"Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic Regions titled neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable in Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition modeled in the Form of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs"* in **Ref. [237]** by Henry Garrett (2023), *"Using the Tool As (Neutrosophic) Failed SuperHyperStable To SuperHyperModel Cancer's Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs"* in **Ref. [240]** by Henry Garrett (2023), *"Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints"* in **Ref. [241]** by Henry Garrett (2023), *"(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer's Recognition by Well-SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs"* in **Ref. [242]** by Henry Garrett (2023), *"Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond"* in **Ref. [243]** by Henry Garrett (2022), *"(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer's Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs"* in **Ref. [244]** by Henry Garrett (2022), *"Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer's Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs"* in **Ref. [245]** by Henry Garrett (2022), *"Basic Neutrosophic Notions Concerning SuperHyperDominating and Neutrosophic SuperHyperResolving in SuperHyperGraph"* in **Ref. [256]** by Henry Garrett (2022), *"Initial Material of Neutrosophic Preliminaries to Study Some Neutrosophic Notions Based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)"* in **Ref. [257]** by Henry Garrett (2022), and [4-257], there are some endeavors to formalize the basic SuperHyperNotions about neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph alongside scientific research books at [258-395]. Two popular scientific research books in Scribd in the terms of high readers, 5679 and 6667 respectively, on neutrosophic science is on [396, 397].

Some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [396]** by Henry Garrett (2023) which is indexed by Google

Scholar and has more than 5679 readers in Scribd. It's titled "*Beyond Neutrosophic Graphs*" and published by Dr. Henry Garrett. This research book covers different types of notions and settings in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory.

Also, some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [397]** by Henry Garrett (2023) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 6667 readers in Scribd. It's titled "*Neutrosophic Duality*" and published by Dr. Henry Garrett. This research book presents different types of notions SuperHyperResolving and SuperHyperDominating in the setting of duality in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory. This research book has scrutiny on the complement of the intended set and the intended set, simultaneously. It's smart to consider a set but acting on its complement that what's done in this research book which is popular in the terms of high readers in Scribd.

See the seminal scientific researches [1–3]. The formalization of the notions on the framework of notions in SuperHyperGraphs, Neutrosophic notions in SuperHyperGraphs theory, and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs theory at [4–257] alongside scientific research books at [258–395]. Two popular scientific research books in Scribd, in the terms of high readers, 5679 and 6667 respectively, on neutrosophic science is on [396, 397].

References

1. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph As Hyper Tool On Super Toot", *Curr Trends Mass Comm* 2(1) (2023) 32-55. (doi: 10.33140/CTMC.02.01.03).
2. Henry Garrett, "*Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer's Treatments*", *J Math Techniques Comput Math* 2(1) (2023) 35-47. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.02.01.05).
3. Henry Garrett, "*A Research on Cancer's Recognition and Neutrosophic Super Hypergraph by Eulerian Super Hyper Cycles and Hamiltonian Sets as Hyper Covering Versus Super separations*", *J Math Techniques Comput Math* 2(3) (2023) 136-148. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.02.03.03).
4. Henry Garrett, "*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction to Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition and Beyond*", *J Math Techniques Comput Math* 2(6) (2023) 221-307. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.02.06.04).
5. Henry Garrett, "*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph by Initial Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Initial Eulogy on Super Initial EULA*", *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research* 3(2) (2023) 60-88. (doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.60-88).
6. Henry Garrett, "*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graph by Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut on Super EULA-Path-Cut*", *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research* 3(2) (2023) 102-124. (doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.102-124).
7. Henry Garrett, "*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graph by Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut on Super EULA-Path-Cut*", *J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res* 2(1) (2023) 16-24. (doi: 10.33140/JCTCSR.02.01.04)

8. Henry Garrett, “*Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes*”, J Math Techniques Comput Math 1(3) (2022) 242-263. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.01.03.09) 1130
1131
1132
1133
9. Garrett, Henry. “0039 — *Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph.*” CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research - Zenodo, Nov. 2022. CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6319942>. 1134
1135
1136
1137
1138
<https://oa.mg/work/10.5281/zenodo.6319942> 1139
10. Garrett, Henry. “0049 — *(Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs.*” CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research - Zenodo, Feb. 2022. CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research, <https://doi.org/10.13140/rg.2.2.35241.26724>. 1140
1141
1142
<https://doi.org/10.13140/rg.2.2.35241.26724>. 1143
<https://oa.mg/work/10.13140/rg.2.2.35241.26724> 1144
11. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010308 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0308.v1). 1145
1146
1147
1148
12. Henry Garrett, “*Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010282 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0282.v1). 1149
1150
1151
1152
13. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010267 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0267.v1). 1153
1154
1155
14. Henry Garrett, “*The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010265 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0265.v1). 1156
1157
1158
1159
1160
1161
15. Henry Garrett, “*Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010262,(doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0262.v1). 1162
1163
1164
1165
16. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010240 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0240.v1). 1166
1167
1168
1169
17. Henry Garrett, “*Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010224, (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0224.v1). 1170
1171
1172
1173
18. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 1174
1175
1176

19. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1).
1177
1178
1179
1180
20. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010044
1181
1182
1183
21. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010043 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0043.v1).
1184
1185
1186
22. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1).
1187
1188
1189
1190
23. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1).
1191
1192
1193
1194
24. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120549 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0549.v1).
1195
1196
1197
25. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120540 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0540.v1).
1198
1199
1200
1201
1202
26. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120500 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0500.v1).
1203
1204
1205
27. Henry Garrett, “*Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120324 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0324.v1).
1206
1207
1208
1209
28. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022110576 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202211.0576.v1).
1210
1211
1212
1213
29. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Strongly Resolving Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17389.97769).
1214
1215
1216
1217
30. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Strongly Resolving Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28685.10727).
1218
1219
1220
1221

31. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Strongly Resolving Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.24994.20169).
1222
1223
1224
1225
32. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Dominating Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10371529).
1226
1227
1228
33. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Dominating Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10299535).
1229
1230
1231
34. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Dominating Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10263440).
1232
1233
1234
1235
35. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By STABLE As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10028600).
1236
1237
1238
36. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By STABLE As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8310454).
1239
1240
1241
37. Henry Garrett, “Recognition of Cancer With Bipartite and Path as Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By the Tool Called Stability”, Preprints 2023, 2023081972 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202308.1972.v1).
1242
1243
1244
38. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By STABLE As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8262182).
1245
1246
1247
39. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By REVERSE CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206877).
1248
1249
1250
1251
40. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By REVERSE CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206834).
1252
1253
1254
1255
41. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By REVERSE CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206773).
1256
1257
1258
1259
42. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By EQUAL CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201319).
1260
1261
1262
1263
43. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By EQUAL CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201255).
1264
1265
1266
1267

44. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By EQUAL CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201165). 1268
1269
1270
1271
45. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8196147). 1272
1273
1274
1275
46. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8196132). 1276
1277
1278
1279
47. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8196099). 1280
1281
1282
1283
48. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8187955). 1284
1285
1286
49. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8161878). 1287
1288
1289
50. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8176262). 1290
1291
1292
51. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperPerfect Search As Hyper Perf On Super Perfidy”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8104836). 1293
1294
1295
52. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Perfidy By Hyper Perf Of SuperHyperPerfect Search In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8104857). 1296
1297
1298
53. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Strict Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8092796). 1299
1300
1301
54. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Reverse Strict Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8092766). 1302
1303
1304
55. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Unequal Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8088438). 1305
1306
1307
56. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Unequal Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8088387). 1308
1309
1310

57. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Strict Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8084436). 1311
1312
1313
58. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Strict Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8084420). 1314
1315
1316
59. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Strict Connective As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8080100). 1317
1318
1319
60. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Reverse Strict Connective In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8080068). 1320
1321
1322
61. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Unequal Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8078445). 1323
1324
1325
62. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Unequal Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8078543). 1326
1327
1328
63. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Strict Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8076416). 1329
1330
1331
64. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Strict Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8076399). 1332
1333
1334
65. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8072171). 1335
1336
1337
66. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Reverse Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8072267). 1338
1339
1340
67. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Equal Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8067384). 1341
1342
1343
68. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Equal Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8067409). 1344
1345
1346
69. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8061927). 1347
1348
1349
70. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8062016). 1350
1351
1352
71. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8057696). 1353
1354
1355

72. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Reverse Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8057753). 1356
1357
1358
73. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Equal Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8052893). 1359
1360
1361
74. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Equal Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8052925). 1362
1363
1364
75. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8051346). 1365
1366
1367
76. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8051360). 1368
1369
1370
77. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By United Dominating As Hyper Ultra On Super Units”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8025707). 1371
1372
1373
78. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Units By Hyper Ultra Of United Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8027275). 1374
1375
1376
79. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Zero Forcing As Hyper ford On Super forceps”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8017246). 1377
1378
1379
80. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super forceps By Hyper ford Of Zero Forcing In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8020128). 1380
1381
1382
81. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Matrix-Based As Hyper mat On Super matte”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7978571). 1383
1384
1385
82. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super mat By Hyper matte Of Matrix-Based In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7978857). 1386
1387
1388
83. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Dominating-Edges As Hyper Dome On Super Eddy”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7940830). 1389
1390
1391
84. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Eddy By Hyper Dome Of Dominating-Edges In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7943578). 1392
1393
1394
85. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Gap As Hyper Gape On Super Gab”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7916595). 1395
1396
1397
86. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Gab By Hyper Gape Of Edge-Gap In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7923632). 1398
1399
1400

87. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904698). 1401
1402
1403
88. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904671). 1404
1405
1406
89. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decompensation”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904529). 1407
1408
1409
1410
90. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Decompensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904401). 1411
1412
1413
1414
91. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7871026). 1415
1416
1417
92. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7874647). 1418
1419
1420
93. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7857856). 1421
1422
1423
94. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Cycle-Neighbor In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7857841). 1424
1425
1426
95. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decompensation”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7855661). 1427
1428
1429
96. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Decompensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Cycle-Decomposition In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7855637). 1430
1431
1432
97. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Eulogy On Super EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7853867). 1433
1434
1435
98. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super EULA By Hyper Eulogy Of Eulerian-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7853922). 1436
1437
1438
99. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Path-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7851519). 1439
1440
1441
100. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Type-Path-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7851550). 1442
1443
1444

101. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Path-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7839333). 1445
1446
1447
102. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Type-Path-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7840206). 1448
1449
1450
103. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Path-Cut As Hyper Eulogy On Super EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7834229). 1451
1452
1453
104. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super EULA By Hyper Eulogy Of Eulerian-Type-Path-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7834261). 1454
1455
1456
105. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7824560). 1457
1458
1459
106. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Path-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7824623). 1460
1461
1462
107. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7819531). 1463
1464
1465
108. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Path-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7819579). 1466
1467
1468
109. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph As Hyper Tool On Super Toot*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7812236). 1469
1470
1471
110. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By initial Eulerian-Path-Cut As Hyper initial Eulogy On Super initial EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809365). 1472
1473
1474
111. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Cut As Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut On Super EULA-Path-Cut*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809358). 1475
1476
1477
112. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super EULA By Hyper Eulogy Of Eulerian-Path-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809219). 1478
1479
1480
113. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Cut As Hyper Eulogy On Super EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809328). 1481
1482
1483
114. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7806767). 1484
1485
1486
115. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7806838). 1487
1488
1489

116. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804238).
1490
1491
1492
1493
117. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804228).
1494
1495
1496
118. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Hamper On Super Hammy*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7799902).
1497
1498
1499
119. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Hammy By Hyper Hamper Of Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804218).
1500
1501
1502
120. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7796334).
1503
1504
1505
121. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7793372).
1506
1507
1508
122. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Hamper On Super Hammy*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7791952).
1509
1510
1511
123. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Hammy By Hyper Hamper Of Hamiltonian-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7791982).
1512
1513
1514
124. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7790026).
1515
1516
1517
125. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Hamiltonian-Neighbor In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7790052).
1518
1519
1520
126. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7787066).
1521
1522
1523
127. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Hamiltonian-Decomposition In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7787094).
1524
1525
1526
128. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cut As Hyper Hamper On Super Hammy*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7781476).
1527
1528
1529
129. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Hammy By Hyper Hamper Of Hamiltonian-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7783082).
1530
1531
1532

130. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Trace-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7777857). 1533
1534
1535
131. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Trace-Neighbor In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7779286). 1536
1537
1538
132. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Trace-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7771831). 1539
1540
1541
133. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Trace-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7772468). 1542
1543
1544
134. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Trace-Cut As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20913.25446). 1545
1546
1547
135. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Tract By Hyper Track Of Trace-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7764916). 1548
1549
1550
136. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11770.98247). 1551
1552
1553
137. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Edge-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.12400.12808). 1554
1555
1556
138. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.22545.10089). 1557
1558
1559
139. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Edge-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29544.34564). 1560
1561
1562
140. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Cut As Hyper Edify On Super Eddy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11377.76644). 1563
1564
1565
141. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Eddy By Hyper Edify Of Edge-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23750.96329). 1566
1567
1568
142. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31366.24641). 1569
1570
1571
143. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Vertex-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34721.68960). 1572
1573
1574
144. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30212.81289). 1575
1576
1577

145. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decompensation By Hyper Decompress Of Vertex-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18468.76169). 1578
1579
1580
146. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Cut As Hyper Vertu On Super Vertigo*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.24288.35842). 1581
1582
1583
147. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Vertigo By Hyper Vertu Of Vertex-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32467.25124). 1584
1585
1586
148. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31025.45925). 1587
1588
1589
149. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulizer By Hyper Nub Of Stable-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17184.25602). 1590
1591
1592
150. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Decompositions As Hyper Stain On Super Stagy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23423.28327). 1593
1594
1595
151. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Stale By Hyper Stalk Of Stable-Decompositions In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28456.44805). 1596
1597
1598
152. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Cut As Hyper Stain On Super Stagy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23525.68320). 1599
1600
1601
153. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Stale By Hyper Stalk Of Stable-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20170.24000). 1602
1603
1604
154. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Neighbors As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36475.59683). 1605
1606
1607
155. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulizer By Hyper Nub Of Clique-Neighbors In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29764.71046). 1608
1609
1610
156. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Decompositions As Hyper Decompile On Super Decommission*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18780.87683). 1611
1612
1613
157. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decompensation By Hyper Decompress Of Clique- Decompositions In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.27169.48487). 1614
1615
1616
158. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Cut As Hyper Click On Super Cliche*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26134.01603). 1617
1618
1619
159. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Cliff By Hyper Cling Of Clique-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.27392.30721). 1620
1621
1622

160. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Space As Hyper Spin On Super Spacy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33028.40321). 1623
1624
1625
161. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By List- Coloring As Hyper List On Super Lisle*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21389.20966). 1626
1627
1628
162. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Lith By Hyper Lite Of List-Coloring In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.16356.04489). 1629
1630
1631
163. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Space As Hyper Sparse On Super Spark*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21756.21129). 1632
1633
1634
164. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Solidarity By Hyper Soul Of Space In Cancer’s Recognition With (Extreme) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30983.68009). 1635
1636
1637
165. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Connectivity As Hyper Disclosure On Super Closure*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28552.29445). 1638
1639
1640
166. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Uniform By Hyper Deformation Of Edge-Connectivity In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.10936.21761). 1641
1642
1643
167. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Connectivity As Hyper Leak On Super Structure*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35105.89447). 1644
1645
1646
168. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super System By Hyper Explosions Of Vertex-Connectivity In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30072.72960). 1647
1648
1649
169. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Tree-Decomposition As Hyper Forward On Super Returns*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31147.52003). 1650
1651
1652
170. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nodes By Hyper Moves Of Tree-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32825.24163). 1653
1654
1655
171. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Chord As Hyper Excellence On Super Excess*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13059.58401). 1656
1657
1658
172. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Gap By Hyper Navigations Of Chord In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11172.14720). 1659
1660
1661
173. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyper(i,j)-Domination As Hyper Controller On Super Waves*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.22011.80165). 1662
1663
1664
174. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Coincidence By Hyper Routes Of SuperHyper(i,j)-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30819.84003). 1665
1666
1667

175. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperEdge-Domination As Hyper Reversion On Super Indirection*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.10493.84962). 1668
1669
1670
176. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Obstacles By Hyper Model Of SuperHyperEdge-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13849.29280). 1671
1672
1673
177. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperK-Domination As Hyper k-Actions On Super Patterns*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19944.14086). 1674
1675
1676
178. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Harmony By Hyper k-Function Of SuperHyperK-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23299.58404). 1677
1678
1679
179. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperK-Number As Hyper k-Partition On Super Layers*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33103.76968). 1680
1681
1682
180. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Gradient By Hyper k-Class Of SuperHyperK-Number In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23037.44003). 1683
1684
1685
181. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperOrder As Hyper Enumerations On Super Landmarks*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35646.56641). 1686
1687
1688
182. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Analogous By Hyper Visions Of SuperHyperOrder In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18030.48967). 1689
1690
1691
183. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperColoring As Hyper Categories On Super Neighbors*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13973.81121). 1692
1693
1694
184. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Relations By Hyper Identifications Of SuperHyperColoring In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34106.47047). 1695
1696
1697
185. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Contradiction By Hyper Detection of SuperHyperDefensive In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13397.09446). 1698
1699
1700
186. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDimension As Hyper Distinguishing On Super Distances*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31956.88961). 1701
1702
1703
187. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Locations By Hyper Differing Of SuperHyperDimension In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15179.67361). 1704
1705
1706
188. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDominating As Hyper Closing On Super Messy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21510.45125). 1707
1708
1709
189. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Missing By Hyper Searching Of SuperHyperDominating In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13121.84321). 1710
1711
1712

190. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperConnected As Hyper Group On Super Surge*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11758.69441). 1713
1714
1715
191. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Outbreak By Hyper Collections Of SuperHyperConnected In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31891.35367). 1716
1717
1718
192. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperTotal As Hyper Covering On Super Infections*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19360.87048). 1719
1720
1721
193. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Extremism By Hyper Treatments Of SuperHyperTotal In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32363.21286). 1722
1723
1724
194. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Isolation By Hyper Perfectness Of SuperHyperPerfect In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23266.81602). 1725
1726
1727
195. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperPerfect As Hyper Idealism On Super Vacancy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19911.37285). 1728
1729
1730
196. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperJoin As Hyper Separations On Super Sorts*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11050.90569). 1731
1732
1733
197. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super connections By Hyper disconnections Of SuperHyperJoin In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17761.79206). 1734
1735
1736
198. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Mixed-Devastations By Hyper Decisions Of SuperHyperDuality In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34953.52320). 1737
1738
1739
199. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition As (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDuality As Hyper Imaginations On Super Mixed-Illustrations*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33275.80161). 1740
1741
1742
200. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition As (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By Path SuperHyperColoring As Hyper Correction On Super Faults*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30182.50241). 1743
1744
1745
201. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Reflections By Hyper Rotations Of Path SuperHyperColoring In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33459.30243). 1746
1747
1748
202. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas As Hyper Deformations On Super Chains In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDensity*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13444.60806). 1749
1750
1751
203. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas As Hyper Ignorance By SuperHyperDensity On Super Resistances In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi:10.13140/RG.2.2.16800.05123). 1752
1753
1754

204. Henry Garrett, “*New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-VI*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29913.80482). 1755
1756
1757
1758
205. Henry Garrett, “*New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-V*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33269.24809). 1759
1760
1761
1762
206. Henry Garrett, “*New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-IV*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34946.96960). 1763
1764
1765
1766
207. Henry Garrett, “*A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-III*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.14814.31040). 1767
1768
1769
1770
208. Henry Garrett, “*A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-II*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15653.17125). 1771
1772
1773
1774
209. Henry Garrett, “*A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-I*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.25719.50089). 1775
1776
1777
1778
210. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Disruptions In Cancer’s Extreme Recognition As Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hyper Plans Called SuperHyperConnectivities*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29441.94562). 1779
1780
1781
1782
211. Henry Garrett, “*Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition As Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperConnectivities As Hyper Diagnosis On Super Mechanism*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17252.24968). 1783
1784
1785
212. Henry Garrett, “*Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By the Criteria of Eulerian and Hamiltonian Type-Sets As Hyper Modified Cycles On Super Mess*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.16652.59525). 1786
1787
1788
213. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian and Hamiltonian In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph On Super Interactions By Hyper Extensions of Cycles*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34583.24485). 1789
1790
1791
214. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth Type-Results on extreme SuperHyperGirth theory and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs Toward Cancer’s extreme Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010396 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0396.v1). 1792
1793
1794
1795
215. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Warns Hyper Landmark of neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth In Super Type-Versions of Cancer’s neutrosophic Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010395 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0395.v1). 1796
1797
1798
1799

216. Henry Garrett, “*The Constructions of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs on the Cancer’s Recognition in The Confrontation With Super Attacks In Hyper Situations By Implementing (Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in The Technical Approaches to Neutralize SuperHyperViews*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26240.51204). 1800
1801
1802
1803
1804
217. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing As the Entrepreneurs on Cancer’s Recognitions To Fail Forcing Style As the Super Classes With Hyper Effects In The Background of the Framework is So-Called (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.12818.73925). 1805
1806
1807
1808
1809
218. Henry Garrett, “*Super Actions On The Types of Hyper Levels In The Sensible Neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth On Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26836.88960). 1810
1811
1812
1813
219. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth Approaches on the Super Challenges on the Cancer’s Recognition In the Hyper Model of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36745.93289). 1814
1815
1816
220. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010308 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0308.v1). 1817
1818
1819
1820
221. Henry Garrett, “*Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010282 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0282.v1). 1821
1822
1823
1824
222. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010267 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0267.v1).). 1825
1826
1827
223. Henry Garrett, “*The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010265 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0265.v1). 1828
1829
1830
1831
1832
1833
224. Henry Garrett, “*Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010262,(doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0262.v1). 1834
1835
1836
1837
225. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010240 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0240.v1). 1838
1839
1840
1841
226. Henry Garrett, “*Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010224, (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0224.v1). 1842
1843
1844
1845

227. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperMatching By (R-)Definitions And Polynomials To Monitor Cancer’s Recognition In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35061.65767). 1846
1847
1848
228. Henry Garrett, “*The Focus on The Partitions Obtained By Parallel Moves In The Cancer’s Extreme Recognition With Different Types of Extreme SuperHyperMatching Set and Polynomial on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18494.15680). 1849
1850
1851
1852
229. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32530.73922). 1853
1854
1855
1856
230. Henry Garrett, “*Indeterminacy On The All Possible Connections of Cells In Front of Cancer’s Attacks In The Terms of Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique on Cancer’s Recognition called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15897.70243). 1857
1858
1859
1860
231. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32530.73922). 1861
1862
1863
1864
232. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 1865
1866
1867
233. Henry Garrett, “*Perfect Directions Toward Idealism in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Forwarding Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30092.80004). 1868
1869
1870
234. Henry Garrett, “*Demonstrating Complete Connections in Every Embedded Regions and Sub-Regions in the Terms of Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClique*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23172.19849). 1871
1872
1873
1874
235. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 1875
1876
1877
1878
236. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1). 1879
1880
1881
1882
237. Henry Garrett, “*Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic Regions titled neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition modeled in the Form of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17385.36968). 1883
1884
1885
1886
238. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010044 1887
1888
1889

239. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010043 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0043.v1). 1890
1891
1892
240. Henry Garrett, “Using the Tool As (Neutrosophic) Failed SuperHyperStable To SuperHyperModel Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28945.92007). 1893
1894
1895
241. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11447.80803). 1896
1897
1898
242. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well-SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35774.77123). 1899
1900
1901
243. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36141.77287). 1902
1903
1904
1905
244. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29430.88642). 1906
1907
1908
245. Henry Garrett, “Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11369.16487). 1909
1910
1911
1912
246. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances”, Preprints 2022, 2022120549 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0549.v1). 1913
1914
1915
247. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19380.94084). 1916
1917
1918
248. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses”, Preprints 2022, 2022120540 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0540.v1). 1919
1920
1921
1922
1923
249. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.14426.41923). 1924
1925
1926
1927
1928
250. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions”, Preprints 2022, 2022120500 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0500.v1). 1929
1930
1931
251. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20993.12640). 1932
1933
1934

252. Henry Garrett, “*Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120324 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0324.v1). 1935
1936
1937
1938
253. Henry Garrett, “*Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23123.04641). 1939
1940
1941
1942
254. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022110576 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202211.0576.v1). 1943
1944
1945
1946
255. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23324.56966). 1947
1948
1949
1950
256. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Neutrosophic Notions Concerning SuperHyperDominating and Neutrosophic SuperHyperResolving in SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29173.86244). 1951
1952
1953
257. Henry Garrett, “*Initial Material of Neutrosophic Preliminaries to Study Some Neutrosophic Notions Based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.25385.88160). 1954
1955
1956
1957
258. Henry Garrett, “Stable Sequence In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10523307). 1958
1959
259. Henry Garrett, “Resolving Sequence In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10395711). 1960
1961
260. Henry Garrett, “Dominating Sequence In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10042973). 1962
1963
261. Henry Garrett, “Stable In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8210033). 1964
1965
262. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Connective Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206898). 1966
1967
263. Henry Garrett, “Equal Connective Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201378). 1968
1969
264. Henry Garrett, “Connective Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8194003). 1970
1971
265. Henry Garrett, “Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8113416). 1972
1973
266. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperPerfect Search In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8104880). 1974
1975
267. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Strict Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8092816). 1976
1977

- 268. Henry Garrett, “Unequal Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8090194). 1978
1979
- 269. Henry Garrett, “Strict Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8086310). 1980
1981
- 270. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Strict Connective In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8080167). 1982
1983
- 271. Henry Garrett, “Unequal Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8078574). 1984
1985
- 272. Henry Garrett, “Strict Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8076449). 1986
1987
- 273. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8072310). 1988
1989
- 274. Henry Garrett, “Equal Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8067469). 1990
1991
- 275. Henry Garrett, “Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8062076). 1992
1993
- 276. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8057817). 1994
1995
- 277. Henry Garrett, “Equal Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8052976). 1996
1997
- 278. Henry Garrett, “Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8051368). 1998
1999
- 279. Henry Garrett, “United Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8027488). 2000
2001
- 280. Henry Garrett, “Zero Forcing In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8020181). 2002
2003
- 281. Henry Garrett, “Matrix-Based In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7978921). 2004
2005
- 282. Henry Garrett, “Collections of Math II”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7943878). 2006
2007
- 283. Henry Garrett, “Dominating-Edges In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7943871). 2008
2009
- 284. Henry Garrett, “Edge-Gap In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7923786). 2010
2011
- 285. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7905287). 2012
2013
- 286. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904586). 2014
2015
- 287. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7874677). 2016
2017

288. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7857906). 2018
2019
289. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7856329). 2020
2021
290. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7854561). 2022
2023
291. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Type-Path-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7851893). 2024
2025
292. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Type-Path-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7848019). 2026
2027
293. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Type-Path-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7835063). 2028
2029
294. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Path-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7826705). 2030
2031
295. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Path-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7820680). 2032
2033
296. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Path-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7812750). 2034
2035
297. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7812142). 2036
2037
298. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7810394). 2038
2039
299. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7807782). 2040
2041
300. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804449). 2042
2043
301. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7793875). 2044
2045
302. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7792307). 2046
2047
303. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7790728). 2048
2049
304. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7787712). 2050
2051
305. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7783791). 2052
2053
306. Henry Garrett, “*Trace-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7780123). 2054
2055
307. Henry Garrett, “*Trace-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7773119). 2056
2057

308. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDuality*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7637762). 2058
2059
309. Henry Garrett, “*Trace-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7766174). 2060
2061
310. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7762232). 2062
2063
311. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7758601). 2064
2065
312. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7754661). 2066
2067
313. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7750995) . 2068
2069
314. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7749875). 2070
2071
315. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7747236). 2072
2073
316. Henry Garrett, “*Stable-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7742587). 2074
2075
317. Henry Garrett, “*Stable-Decompositions In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7738635). 2076
2077
318. Henry Garrett, “*Stable-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7734719). 2078
2079
319. Henry Garrett, “*Clique-Neighbors In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7730484). 2080
2081
320. Henry Garrett, “*Clique-Decompositions In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7730469). 2082
2083
321. Henry Garrett, “*Clique-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7722865). 2084
2085
322. Henry Garrett, “*Space In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7713563). 2086
2087
323. Henry Garrett, “*Space In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7709116). 2088
2089
324. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Connectivity In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7706415). 2090
2091
325. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Connectivity In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7706063). 2092
2093
326. Henry Garrett, “*Tree-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7701906). 2094
2095
327. Henry Garrett, “*Chord In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7700205). 2096
2097

- 328. Henry Garrett, “*(i,j)*-Domination In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7694876). 2098
2099
- 329. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Domination In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7679410). 2100
2101
- 330. Henry Garrett, “*K-Domination In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7675982). 2102
2103
- 331. Henry Garrett, “*K-Number In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7672388). 2104
2105
- 332. Henry Garrett, “*Order In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7668648). 2106
2107
- 333. Henry Garrett, “*Coloring In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7662810). 2108
2109
- 334. Henry Garrett, “*Dimension In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7659162). 2110
2111
- 335. Henry Garrett, “*Cancer In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653233). 2112
2113
- 336. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperWheel*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653204). 2114
2115
- 337. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperMultipartite*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653142). 2116
2117
- 338. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperBipartite*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653117). 2118
2119
- 339. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperStar*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653089). 2120
2121
- 340. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7651687). 2122
2123
- 341. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperPath*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7651619). 2124
2125
- 342. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDomination*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7651439). 2126
2127
- 343. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7650729). 2128
2129
- 344. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperConnected*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7647868). 2130
2131
- 345. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperTotal*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7647017). 2132
2133
- 346. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperPerfect*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7644894). 2134
2135
- 347. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperJoin*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7641880). 2136
2137

348. Henry Garrett, “*Path SuperHyperColoring*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7632923). 2138
2139
349. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDensity*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7623459). 2140
2141
350. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnectivities*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7606416). 2142
2143
351. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperConnectivities*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7606416). 2144
2145
352. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperConnectivities*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7606404). 2146
2147
353. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7580018). 2148
2149
354. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7580018). 2150
2151
355. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7580018). 2152
2153
356. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7579929). 2154
2155
357. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563170). 2156
2157
358. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563164). 2158
2159
359. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563160). 2160
2161
360. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563160). 2162
2163
361. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563160). 2164
2165
362. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7557063). 2166
2167
363. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7557009). 2168
2169
364. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7539484). 2170
2171
365. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2172
2173
366. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2174
2175
367. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2176
2177

368. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 2178
10.5281/zenodo.7574952). 2179
369. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 2180
10.5281/zenodo.7574992). 2181
370. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 2182
10.5281/zenodo.7523357). 2183
371. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 2184
10.5281/zenodo.7523357). 2185
372. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2186
2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2187
373. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 2188
(doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2189
374. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2190
2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2191
375. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 2192
10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2193
376. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 2194
10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2195
377. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 2196
10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2197
378. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2198
2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7497450). 2199
379. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 2200
(doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7497450). 2201
380. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 2202
(doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2203
381. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 2204
10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2205
382. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 2206
(doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2207
383. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 2208
(doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2209
384. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 2210
10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2211
385. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 2212
(doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2213
386. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 2214
10.5281/zenodo.7539484). 2215
387. Henry Garrett, “*Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 2216
10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2217

388. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523357). 2218
2219
389. Henry Garrett, “*Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2220
2221
390. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2222
2223
391. Henry Garrett, “*Failed SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7497450). 2224
2225
392. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2226
2227
393. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2228
2229
394. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7480110). 2230
2231
395. Henry Garrett, “*Neut. SuperHyperEdges*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7378758). 2232
2233
396. Henry Garrett, “*Beyond Neutrosophic Graphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6320305). 2234
2235
397. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Duality*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6677173). 2236
2237